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Characteristics of Yan Zhao Folk art and the challenges and opportunities of its translation- taking Yan Zhao paper-cutting and tea culture as examples

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Abstract

This article briefly introduces the Yan-Zhao culture, as well as the development history of Yan-Zhao paper-cutting and tea art, and introduces the characteristics of these two folk arts in detail. It also studies the translation situation of these two folk arts, mainly focusing on the plight and challenges they faced in translation. For example: inadequate theory, unique cultural symbols that are difficult to translate, significant differences between Chinese and foreign cultures, and the difficulty in conveying the implicit content of folk culture and art. At the same time, the article explores the opportunities that can be seized in the current translation of folk arts, such as the new impetus to translation brought by the development of artificial intelligence, the promotion of national voice in international environment, and the opportunities brought by increased national and people-to-people exchanges. With these opportunities in mind, the article provides some ideas and suggestions for solving translation problems.

Keywords: Yan Zhao Culture; Folk Art; Characteristics Of Yan Zhao Folk Art; Translation Of Folk Art; Challenges And Opportunities For The Translation Of Folk Art.

1. Introduction

1.1. Yan Zhao Culture

The Yan-Zhao culture holds an important position in the history of Chinese civilization and is an important branch of ancient culture. It also forms the background of the culture in present-day Hebei Province. The Yan-Zhao area has been a significant strategic location in Chinese history, with a long history and rich cultural heritage. The birthplace of Yan-Zhao culture refers to the area where the ancient states of Yan and Zhao were located in ancient time. Yan, an important vassal state during the Spring and Autumn Period (507-444 BC), it roughly covers the central part of Hebei Province and Beijing. Zhao, located in the southern part of Yan, and lies on the southern part of Hebei Province, the northern part of Shanxi Province, and the western part of Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region. This land has witnessed the rise and fall of multiple dynasties and kingdoms, such as the states of Yan and Zhao during the Spring and Autumn period (507-444 BC). Due to its significant geographical location and historical background, the Yan-Zhao region carries rich historical memories and cultural traditions, which contribute to its profound cultural heritage. Since ancient times, the Yan-Zhao region has possessed diverse cultural traditions and historical relics.

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2. Development History and Characteristics of Yan Zhao Paper-Cutting and Tea Art

2.1. Development History

Folk art in the Yan-Zhao region has a long history, including various forms such as woodcarving, ceramics, and embroidery. As early as the Warring States period (475 BC-221 BC), there were already diverse forms of folk art in the Yan-Zhao region. The aristocrats and wealthy merchants often hired craftsmen to make handicrafts such as woodcarving, jade, and ceramics. These handicrafts were often used to decorate palaces, temples, and condo of noble residences, showcasing the prosperity and high cultural level of society at that time.

The Ming and Qing dynasties were also an important stage in the development of folk art in the Yan-Zhao region. During this period, woodcarving, ceramics, embroidery, and other art forms developed in large-scale and received good inheritance in the Yan-Zhao region. For example, Zhengding County in Hebei Province is a famous hometown of woodcarving in China. The woodcarvers who lived in Ming and Qing dynasty were well-known for their unique innovation and superior craftsmanship. Meanwhile, the ceramic craftsmanship in the Yan-Zhao region also reached a high level, and products were sold well in both domestic market and abroad. In addition, embroidery is also a traditional folk art in the Yan-Zhao region, which was widely developed and applied during these dynasties.

After entering the 20th century, with the progress of modernization and social changes, folk art in the Yan-Zhao region faced new challenges and opportunities. Folk art gradually transformed into part of the cultural industry and combined with various fields such as tourism and education. In summary, folk art in the Yan-Zhao region has a long history and rich connotations. From ancient times to modern times, the art forms of paper cutting, woodcarving, ceramics, tea culture, embroidery, and more in the region have gone through a long development process and have become an important part of traditional Chinese culture. At the same time, how to help folk art with local characteristics to go to the world is also a major challenge.

2.2. Characteristics of Yan-Zhao Paper-Cutting Art

The unique characteristic of Yan-Zhao folk art represents the traditional culture and customs of the area. For example, Yan-Zhao paper cutting has a long history and is known as one of the birthplaces of Chinese paper cutting. It is famous for its unique knife skills and smooth lines, which are often used in the production of decorations such as New Year paintings and window flowers. Its history can be traced back several hundred years. It is said that Yan-Zhao paper cutting originated from farmers using scissors and paper for handicrafts during their leisure time, gradually spreading and developing as a decoration in traditional festivals such as temple fairs and weddings.

The skills of Yan-Zhao paper cutting are very exquisite and requires long-term learning and practice to master. The paper cutting patterns are diverse, and each pattern requires artists to be meticulous. In addition, the paper cutting also pays attention to the use of color, not only increasing the visual effects of the works, but also making them more attractive and enjoyable. At the same time, Yan-Zhao paper cutting often combines with other art forms, such as painting and embroidery, to enrich the expression and connotation of the works. It carries people's yearning for a better life and a better vision.

In recent years, with the prosperity of tourism and the increase in cultural exchanges, Yan-Zhao paper cutting has gradually gone abroad and gained international recognition. More and more people have begun to pay attention to and appreciate it, to the art form which passed down from generation to generation for thousands of years. As an important part of Chinese traditional culture, the paper cutting not only represents the unique artistic style, but also has become an important symbol of Chinese traditional culture.

In summary, Yan-Zhao paper cutting is a traditional paper cutting art form with unique characteristics, with a long history and exquisite skills. With its beautiful lines and rich and colorful patterns, it has attracted more and more attention from people. It is not only a decorative art, but also carries people's yearning for a better life and traditional culture. Through the inheritance and development of paper cutting art, we can better understand and experience the profound and extensive Chinese traditional culture.

Tea Culture: The Yan-Zhao region has a rich tea culture, with unique forms of expression in tea art. Tea masters show their love and pursuit of tea culture in the ritual of brewing and tasting tea.

The origin of tea culture in the region can be traced back to ancient times. According to historical records, during the Song Dynasty, tea cultivation and consumption became widespread in the Yan-Zhao region. People realized the refreshing and revitalizing effects of tea, gradually developing a love and admiration for it. Tea not only became an essential beverage in people's daily lives but also entered the cultural circles of the imperial court and literati.

Over time, the tea culture in the region gradually developed and flourished. Tea ceremonies became important social activities, widely practiced during banquets, gatherings, and meetings. Tea masters, through careful training and practice, mastered a series of unique brewing techniques, elevating the art of tea. Tea ceremonies not only emphasize the brewing process but also pay attention to the selection and presentation of tea utensils, as well as interaction and communication with the audience. This cultural tradition not only enriches people's lives but also transforms tea culture into a distinctive art form.

2.3. Characteristics of Yan-Zhao Tea Art

In the Yan-Zhao region, there is a rich variety of tea types. Black tea, green tea, yellow tea, white tea, and oolong tea all have their own characteristics and charm. For example, black tea is known for its unique aroma and mellow taste, earning the place the reputation as the "home of black tea." Green tea is highly praised for its refreshing taste, richness in antioxidants, among other benefits. Every type of tea has its unique charm and appeal, reflecting the distinctive allure of Yan-Zhao's tea culture in both taste and production processes. In addition to tea itself, Yan-Zhao tea culture has also integrated various related arts and traditions. For instance, tea opera is a unique feature of Yan-Zhao tea culture. In this performance form, actors incorporate tea brewing and drinking into their singing, recitation, and actions to show tea's beauty. Tea opera is not only entertaining but also conveys profound cultural connotations, becoming an essential part of Yan-Zhao's tea culture.

Furthermore, there are many traditional festivals and events related to tea culture in the region. For example, the tea-picking festival is an annual grand event where people invite friends and family to participate in tea-picking activities while holding various exhibitions and celebrations. Activities such as tea art competitions, tea exhibitions, and lectures are also frequently held, attracting numerous tea culture enthusiasts and experts.

Tea culture is not only an integral part of daily life for the people in the place, but also an embodiment of cultural traditions and artistic forms. With a long and rich history, tea culture enables people to appreciate tea's aroma and taste, experience the beauty of tea art performances, and feel the tranquility and comfort that tea brings. Its unique charm not only attracts local residents but also increasingly more tourists from both domestic and international destinations.

3. Challenges in translating Yan-Zhao paper-cutting and tea culture

3.1. Insufficient theoretical foundation and constraints from unique cultural symbols

Folk art is highly characterized by local features and contains many distinctive cultural symbols. Language serves as a bridge for communication among people from different countries and cultures. When conducting cultural promotion, the first issue to consider is how to express the desired effects in another language and achieve our expectations for external publicity. However, the research on the translation of Yan-Zhao folk art is insufficient currently, which makes it difficult to achieve the expected results in translating these highly unique local art forms. This situation not only hinders the "go global" of local art with distinct characteristics but also leads to missed opportunities for international cultural exchanges. As a result, Yan-Zhao folk art finds it challenging to demonstrate its strength, enrich its connotations, and develop innovatively in collisions and blends with different cultures.

Especially when translating unique cultural symbols, we often encounter many translation obstacles. Taking tea culture translation as an example, due to the climatic conditions in the region being suitable for the growth of tea trees, there are many tea tree varieties in this area. These varieties encompass large-leaf types, small-leaf types, and oolong types and so on. Among them, Yanshan Xueya tea and Laiyuan Maojian tea are famous in China. When translating these different types of tea, we need to put in a lot of effort to investigate their respective characteristics and express them appropriately. For example, there is no direct English equivalent for "雪芽茶" (Xueya tea). Therefore, we can only use suitable English expressions based on fully understanding its characteristics. At the same time, our translation should enable the target audience to accurately comprehend the intended meaning. After reading the translation, they should have a rough concept and ideally achieve the same effect as the original Chinese text.

In addition to tea tree cultivation, the region also has unique forms of tea art performance, including tea brewing, tea tasting, and tea pouring. In the process of tea art performance, tea artists pursue not only the brewing process but also the aesthetics involved. Smooth movements and graceful demeanor are aspects that tea artists particularly value. Moreover, tea art emphasizes etiquette. Tea ceremony etiquette emphasizes both manners and emotional communication. People live in the area like to use tea etiquette to entertain guests, brewing tea with meticulous care, and paying attention to expressing respect and care for guests while pouring tea. Tea utensils have unique symbolic meanings. For example, a teapot symbolizes family reunion and warmth, while a teacup represents friendship and beauty. Thus, it requires translators to not only translate the literal meaning but also capture the implied meanings. For instance, “茶杯” (teacups) cannot be simply understood as a teacup, because in this region, teacups carry beautiful meanings beyond their names. Apart from the name, the translation should also convey its implied significance. When translating these elements, we need to think about how to convey the cultural connotations to foreign readers or audiences. This is the issue we need to contemplate and solve.

3.2. Cultural Differences between Chinese and Western Culture

The differences between Chinese and foreign cultures are significant, primarily manifested in values, etiquette, thinking styles, and daily habits, among other aspects. Particularly, something unique to a culture may be well-known in one place but completely unfamiliar to people in another place. For example, in ancient China, we had many advanced and distinctive cultural elements that existed in the lives of the Chinese people and had a subtle influence on everyone. Folk art, as mentioned earlier, is an art form well understood by the Chinese people, but when translating it into a foreign language, cultural differences need to be taken into account. For instance, in countries without a tea-drinking culture, how should we translate the act of drinking tea and the cultural forms associated with it to allow non-native speakers to experience the same feelings towards tea culture as native speakers? In addition, the characteristics of each type of tea cannot be overlooked; otherwise, non-native speakers will not understand the specific connotations of tea, and relying solely on phonetic transliteration is far from sufficient. For example, the terms “生” (raw) and “熟” (ripe) in relation to tea, if translated directly as “raw” and “ripe,” would be baffling because when Chinese people say “生茶” (raw tea), they mainly refer to unfermented tea leaves, while “熟茶” (ripe tea) refers to fermented tea leaves. However, in English, “raw” and “ripe” primarily denote the degree of ripeness. Therefore, having a deep understanding of both languages and cultural backgrounds is a basic requirement, and adjustments to the translation must be made to accommodate these differences.

3.3. Conveying the Context and Implicit Meaning of the Source Text

When it comes to translation, one crucial aspect that cannot be overlooked is context. A sentence can vary greatly due to different contexts, so when translating, we often first consider the contextual information and then process the text accordingly. Symbols in any language and every sentence cannot exist completely independent of their contexts. In the process of English translation, whether it is translating tea culture, Yan-Zhao paper cutting, or other culturally distinctive symbols, as well as unique cultural activities, it is difficult to translate them without considering the context or disregarding their hidden meanings. Folk art is a particularly distinctive cultural component, and the cultural composition of the text is also an important aspect of translation. Language holds a special position within cultural composition; thus, it is even more necessary to combine it with the context during translation.

Translating Yan-Zhao folk art faces the challenge of cultural differences between different languages. It requires considering how to accurately convey its characteristics and connotations while also taking into account the natural fluency and aesthetic appeal of the language.

4. Opportunities for Translation of Yan-Zhao Paper-cut and Tea Culture

4.1. Development of AI Technology

In recent years, major companies have made significant breakthroughs in AI, and machine translation has also been developing rapidly, bringing many opportunities to the translation work today. For example, machine translation can reduce labor costs and compress the time required for translation. At the same time, artificial intelligence can help translators solve many challenges in cross-cultural communication, bridging barriers between different cultures. In addition, the current application of artificial intelligence has incorporated learning capabilities. It can not only translate words into another language but also review previous context and deeply understand sentences. It can combine the context to assist in finding more appropriate answers, thus better addressing the obstacles posed by language context and hidden meanings in translation work. Furthermore, the vast database possessed by artificial intelligence is a powerful tool that translators can rely on in the translation process. It may be difficult for individuals to find suitable

translation methods at once solely based on personal accumulation, but the powerful algorithms of artificial intelligence can provide multiple options for translators to refer to and choose from.

4.2. Increased International Status and Foreign Exchange

The development of the cultural industry has been increasingly valued and its status has significantly risen, which has brought many opportunities for cultural dissemination and translation work. In addition, there has been a significant increase in the country's and people's foreign exchanges, such as the implementation and promotion of China's "One Belt, One Road" strategy in recent years, which has made communication between China and countries along the line more closely connected. Large-scale global events like the Winter Olympics and Universiade also increase opportunities for exchanges. With more exchanges, language and cultural barriers will gradually decrease, which will be helpful for translation. Moreover, with the rapid construction and development of the Xiong'an New Area in recent years, it will undoubtedly bring more opportunities for the dissemination of Yan-Zhao culture in the future.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, though the dissemination of Yan-Zhao folk art and culture currently faces many challenges, there are also numerous opportunities in the era. As translators, our task is to seek solutions to overcome these challenges and seize opportunities to excel in translation work. We should strive to disseminate and promote the rich local cultural art forms of our country, enrich the artistic expressions and cultural content of the Chinese nation, and present China's cultural identity in a more comprehensive manner.

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